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Pinna nobilis in the Mar Menor coastal lagoon: a story of colonization and uncertainty

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1 models. The main environmental variables that determined the dispersion and colonization
2 of the bivalve in the lagoon before 2016 are also identified.

3
4 **Key words:** Coastal lagoon; *Pinna nobilis*; hypersalinity; SDMs models; Machine learning;
5 Random Forest

6 **1. INTRODUCTION**

7 The “fan mussel” (*Pinna nobilis* Linnaeus, 1758) is a Mediterranean endemic filter-
8 feeding bivalve, the largest Mediterranean bivalve and one of the largest in the world,
9 attaining lengths up to 120 cm (Zavodnik et al. 1991). According to Butler et al. (1993), it
10 colonizes coastal areas with salinity ranging from 35 psu to 42 psu, at depths between 0.5
11 and 60 m, and mostly in soft-sediment areas overgrown by meadows of the seagrasses
12 *Posidonia oceanica*, *Cymodocea nodosa*, *Zostera marina* and *Zostera noltei* (Zavodnik
13 1967, Zavodnik et al. 1991) or sandy bottoms (Katsanevakis 2007). The population of *P.*
14 *nobilis* in the Mediterranean Sea had been greatly reduced during the last few decades as a
15 result of recreational and commercial fishing, collection by divers and incidental killing by
16 anchoring (Rabaoui et al. 2011). But the real crisis came when from early autumn 2016 a
17 mass mortality event (MME) was detected, impacting *P. nobilis* throughout the western
18 Mediterranean Sea due to a parasite *Haplosporidium pinnae* (Darriba 2017, Catanese et al.
19 2018, Cabanellas-Reboredo et al. 2019). Carella et al. (2019) also found evidences that a
20 *Mycopacterium* species could have a major role in the MME. Specimens of all sizes, depth
21 ranges and habitat types were affected, and the mortality has reached 100% in most
22 populations (Vázquez-Luis et al. 2017). The rapid collapse of the population caused
23 concern and a change of status from the "Vulnerable" category to "Critically endangered"
24 with a serious risk of extinction (Orden TEC / 1078/2018). Since then, the epidemic has
25 spread through much of the Mediterranean; however, coastal lagoons seem to be places
26 where the mortality has not spread (Tsatiris et al. 2018, Panarese et al. 2019).

27 Coastal lagoons are transitional and dynamic zones separated from the ocean by
28 geographical and ecological barriers; they are shallow inland water bodies connected with
29 the sea by one or more restricted inlets which remain open at least intermittently (Kjerfve
30 1994). Coastal lagoons are controlled by complex interactions between land, ocean and

1 atmosphere. The ecotone character of coastal lagoons makes them diverse, dynamic and
2 fragile systems (Giménez-Casalduero 2006, Viaroli et al. 2007). However, human activities
3 cause changes in the processes and ecological interactions of these ecosystems (Basset et al.
4 2008), and the increasingly intensive agricultural activity that takes place in the land of the
5 surrounding areas increases nutrient inputs and can even provoke severe episodes of
6 eutrophication (McGlathery et al. 2007).

7 The Mar Menor is a hypersaline coastal lagoon, located in a semi-arid region of south-
8 eastern Spain. Its insulation has caused extreme environmental conditions, such as
9 temperature stress (with abrupt temperature changes even daily) and high salinity, which
10 have allowed the presence of communities dominated by euryhaline and eurythermal
11 species that generated a characteristic landscape (Mas et al. 2017). In 1976, one of the inlets
12 (Estacio) was dredged and widened, making it 30 m wide and 5 m deep (Mas 1994). This
13 connection modified the hydrodynamic regime of the lagoon, altering the water renewal
14 rate. As a consequence, its sedimentary nature changed, salinity decreased, and annual and
15 daily temperature changes were damped, approaching values similar to those of the
16 Mediterranean Sea (Baraza et al. 2003, Lloret et al. 2005). As a result, ecological barriers
17 were weakened, allowing the entry and establishment of new species in the lagoon, one of
18 them was *P. nobilis*. The species that have colonized the lagoon since the widening of the
19 inlet vary from the typically Mediterranean *P. nobilis* to species considered invasive such
20 as the bivalve *Bursatella leachii* De Blainville, 1817 (Zenetos et al. 2004), or the blue crab
21 (*Callinectes sapidus* Rathbun, 1896) (Gimenez-Casalduero et al. 2016).

22 Although *P. nobilis* is a common bivalve in semi-closed bays and Mediterranean coastal
23 lagoons (Katsanevakis 2004), it was absent from the Mar Menor until the early 1980s,
24 when was observed by Rodríguez Babio & Navarro Tárrega (1983) and Murillo & Talavera
25 (1983), and in a few years became an important component of the benthos (Belando et al.
26 2014). To model their potential habitat up to 2015, it is important to know the routes of
27 entry into the lagoon and the environmental factors that determined its spread and
28 colonization patterns in the lagoon. After this wide stabilization process, in 2016 a high
29 mortality event occurred in the Mar Menor. All the results indicate that the cause of this
30 mortality is not due to the *Haplosporidium pinnae* epidemic (Catanese et al. 2018), but the
31 environmental collapse that occurred in the lagoon in 2016.

1 This environmental collapse started in the second half of 2015, when, after decades of
2 nutrient and phytosanitary inputs from nearby agricultural activities, the Mar Menor coastal
3 lagoon underwent a Harmful Algal Bloom (HABs) event. In spring 2016, the situation had
4 reached a dramatic peak, the high concentration of phytoplankton prevented the light from
5 reaching the deeper areas of the lagoon, limiting photosynthesis in these areas (CACMM
6 2017). The vegetation below the new photic threshold died and the organic matter which
7 accumulated on the bottom caused processes of hypoxia and anoxia. The absence of oxygen
8 caused the death of the entire benthic community below 3 m depth and more than 85% of
9 the lagoon surface was affected (Belando et al. 2017).

10 We have estimated the potential distribution and density of *P. nobilis* using species
11 distribution models (SDMs). The advantage of this type of methods is that
12 environmental/geographic information is used to explain observed patterns of species
13 presence or abundance and density (Elith & Graham 2009). In this study a machine
14 learning approach was used, which is a more robust alternative to parametric methods. The
15 complex nature of ecological systems hinders our ability to generate accurate models using
16 the traditional frequentist data model. Problems such as complex non-linear interactions,
17 spatial and temporal autocorrelation, high dimensionality, homocedasticity or multivariate
18 normality are difficult to address by these methods, whereas they are more easily dealt with
19 by machine learning algorithms (Evans et al. 2011). Although the application of SDMs to
20 the marine environment has not been widespread, recent technological advances in the
21 collection and analysis of data has increasingly facilitated their use in wildlife habitat
22 evaluation. Reiss et al. (2015) highlighted the importance of such methods in marine
23 benthic ecosystems, and extensively reviewed the most used and their applications.

24 The main objectives of this study were (1) to characterise the *P. nobilis* population in the
25 lagoon before the environmental collapse of 2016, (2) identify the main entry routes into
26 the lagoon and analyse the colonization process before 2016, (3) identify the main factors
27 that determine the distribution of the species in the lagoon and (4) carry out a first
28 approximation of the situation of the *P. nobilis* lagoon population after the eutrophication
29 crisis.

30

31

1 2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2 2.1. Study site

3 The Mar Menor (Fig. 1), located in the south-western Mediterranean Sea (37°42'00"N
4 00°47'00"W), is the largest coastal lagoon in the western Mediterranean. It covers an area of
5 135 km² with a mean depth of 3.5 m and a maximum of 7 m. The lagoon is the lowest area
6 of the Campo de Cartagena basin. This basin has an extension of 12,500 ha and there are
7 water inputs by 13 ephemeral channels that flow into the lagoon. The Rambla del Albuñón
8 (66,700 ha) is the most important watercourse both in extension and in sediment and
9 nutrient flows (Fig. 1B). It is a strongly anthropized area, mainly due to the expansion of
10 intensive irrigation agriculture and tourism in the last few decades. Such activities are
11 located very close to the lagoon, generating many environmental problems, because of their
12 intensification that has resulted in a modification of water and nutrient flows (Esteve-Selma
13 et al. 2016).

14 The area is characterized by low precipitation (<300 mm yr⁻¹), high insolation and
15 irradiation, and high evaporation rates. Because of these factors, it is a hypersaline (38-47
16 psu) with warmer waters in summer and colder in winter relative to the adjacent
17 Mediterranean Sea (10-32 °C). Connection of the lagoon with the Mediterranean Sea was
18 limited due to the presence of a sand bar called La Manga, crossed by three very shallow
19 channels (Lillo 1979, López-Bermúdez et al. 1981). But the Estacio canal widening
20 increased the connection between the lagoon and the Mediterranean and caused a decrease
21 in salinity, which meant the elimination of one of the main environmental barriers for the
22 survival of most species. The drop-in salinity favoured the entry and colonization of new
23 species from the Mediterranean. The surveys carried out by Murillo & Talavera (1981) for
24 the Mar Menor malacological study, did not detect the presence of *P. nobilis* in the lagoon.
25 It was in 1982 when the first specimens were identified (Rodríguez Babio & Navarro
26 Tarrega 1983).

27 2.2. *Pinna nobilis* data

28 In this study, several sources of information were used to analyse the colonization and
29 dispersal processes of *Pinna nobilis* in the lagoon, (Fig. 2): (A) Historical data, obtained
30 from published data (Rodríguez Babio & Navarro Tarrega 1983) and Murcia Region Sites

1 of Community Importance (SCI) database (CARM 2003); (B) Integrated 2013-14 data-set
2 and complementary 2016 data-set (to estimate the surviving specimens for that year),
3 obtained from specific sampling surveys carried out for the present study (2013 and 2016),
4 and published data (Belando et al. 2014). Table 1 summarizes the data-sets used in this
5 study.

6 2.2.1. Historical data

7 The location where the first *P. nobilis* specimens were recorded in 1983 was included
8 (Fig. 2A) (Rodríguez Babio & Navarro Tárrega 1983). In order to characterize the species
9 distribution in 2003-04, the Murcia Region marine LIC database was used (Fig. 2A). This
10 database includes 1646 presence/absence observation points sampled during 2003 and
11 2004; however, it is a very unbalanced data-set with 34 presence observations and 1611
12 absence points due to the kind of sampling that was carried out aimed at monitoring the
13 lagoon habitats. Data comes from the database of marine SCIs of the autonomous
14 community of the region of Murcia. Scuba diving and snorkel transects were made for
15 mapping the biocenoses and key species such as seahorse, sea needle or fan mussel
16 presence were recorded (CARM 2003). Some biocenoses (such as sandy areas near the
17 shore), with a very scarce presence of *P. nobilis*, were oversampled.

18 Using an imbalanced data-set to train a classification algorithm may produce a bias
19 towards the most frequent class, negatively impacting the model's performance (Krawczyk
20 2016). A high specificity but a low degree of sensitivity can be obtained, which affects the
21 results when calculating presence probability. Kuhn & Johnson (2013) describe several
22 strategies to solve such problems when modelling, and they recommend a cluster-based
23 selection strategy to specify points with similar environmental conditions based on the
24 input covariates. In order to implement this strategy, a distance-based filtering was, firstly,
25 performed to eliminate observations with a distance of less than 20 from each other (in the
26 data set there are 674 observations that have at least one second point at this distance).
27 Second, a stratified down-sampling of the absence data was performed. The strata (5 areas)
28 were obtained by a hierarchical cluster method based on Strauss & von Maltitz (2017):
29 Manhattan distance for dissimilarity, Wald's method for aggregation and the same variables
30 used to fit the model (Fig. 2A). Inside each stratum a number of points proportional to the

1 total of points in it were randomly removed. As a result, a new data-set was obtained with
2 84 points (35 presences and 49 absences, Fig. 2A).

3 *2.2.2. Integrated 2013-14 data-set and 2016 data-set*

4 Six surveys were conducted over a period of eight months, between March and October
5 2013 (Fig. 2B). The lagoon was divided into a 49 square grid (Fig. 2B) with a base
6 resolution of 2000 m to obtain maximum spatial coverage to characterize the presence and
7 density distribution of the bivalve. A total of 60 density measure fan mussel density were
8 sampled. Specifically, 29 stations of SCUBA diving took place and three line transects of
9 30 m long and 2 m width were carried out in each station. All individuals within the
10 transect were counted.

11 Additionally, 25 density measurements were conducted by bathyscaphe. Thus a 200 long
12 visual sampling area of two m width was surveyed. All specimens within the transects area
13 were counted.

14 This sampling was complemented with two line transects using aquaplane by SCUBA
15 diving covering the first one 2007 m and the second 2633 m long and both 2 m wide in the
16 deepest areas (Buckland et al 2001). The diver with the aquaplane was dragged at a speed
17 of approximately 0.5 m / s and the working depth was 1 to 1.5 m above the bottom. As a
18 safety measure, the diver was dragging a small buoy. The track line was geo-referenced
19 from the boat using a GPS (Garmin e-Trex 20) and every minute during the line depth was
20 measured using a portable depth sounder (Hondex PS7). The start and end time of the line
21 was recorded and synchronized between the diver and the boat. The diver recorded the
22 number of specimens found along the route and the minute of the observation. The first
23 track was divided into 11 transects and the second one into 14 transects at a distance of
24 approximately 175 m. The average density of 3 randomly selected transects was estimated
25 at the beginning, middle and end of the track. So 3 density data were obtained for each
26 aquaplane line. The position of each transect was calculated by crossing the time recorded
27 by the sampler with the vessel's track data.

28 A total of 57 sampling stations were incorporated from the Belando et al (2014) results.
29 According to the authors the sampling was carried out by scuba diving. Three transects of
30 200 m long and 2 m width were made (Belando et al. 2014).

1 The data-set from the 2013 field sampling and the 2014 data-set were merged and used
2 to fit a presence-absence model in the lagoon. After checking the quality of the points, 117
3 were selected with 65 absences and 52 presences (Fig. 2D).

4 Additionally, after the environmental collapse of 2016 caused by an eutrophication
5 process, a survey was carried out to estimate the surviving specimens. A total of 17 scuba
6 diving station were sampled with the same methodology described above. Three transects
7 (30x2) were carried out in each station. All individuals within the transect were counted.
8 All density data were standardized to number of *Pinna nobilis* per 100 m².

9 **2.3. Environmental data**

10 Eleven spatially distributed environmental variables were considered for the regression
11 models. In the case of the variables obtained from data points (sediment granulometry,
12 organic matter content, salinity and depth), interpolation surfaces were obtained using
13 ordinary kriging (OK) and directional semivariograms or an omnidirectional
14 semivariogram if there were not significant differences among the directional
15 semivariogram. We used the R package *automap* (Hiemstra et al. 2009), which allows the
16 automatization of a weighted least squares optimal estimation of semivariogram parameters
17 using the Gauss-Newton algorithm.

18 To characterize the sediment during the 2013 campaign, two cores (5 cm diameter and
19 20 cm length) in the sampling area per square were collected. The granulometric analysis
20 was performed manually in a sieve column according to the Wentworth granulometric
21 scale, and the organic matter of the sediment was determined using the Walkley and Black
22 method (Buchanan 1984). The physicochemical variables of the water column (temperature
23 and salinity) were taken at the epicentre of each square using a CTD sensor simultaneously
24 with density campaigns.

25 The variables with their sources and processing methods are described below: i) Depth
26 (DEPTH), obtained from bathymetric curves and depth points available from the eco-
27 cartographic studies from the *Dirección General de Sostenibilidad de la Costa y el Mar*
28 (EcoMag 2009); ii) Distance to the shore (DSH); iii) to v) Distance to the channels
29 connecting the lagoon and the Mediterranean Sea: Estacio channel (DEST), Encañizadas
30 channel (DENC) and Marchamalo channel (DMAR) (Fig. 1C); vi) Distance to the Rambla

1 del Albuji3n outlet (DALB); vii) percentage of silt (SILT, diameter < 0.063 mm), viii)
2 percentage of sand (SAND, $1 \leq \text{diameter} \leq 0.063$ mm.) and ix) percentage of gravel
3 (GRAV, diameter > 1 mm.); x) organic matter (MO); xi) salinity (SAL) interpolated with
4 OK from data compiled previously (Gonz3lez-Wangüemert et al. 2006, Gonz3lez-
5 Wangüemert et al. 2009). In addition, the X and Y coordinates (XCOOR and YCOOR)
6 were also used as predictors as a simple alternative to indicate the trend of geographic
7 space (Evans et al. 2011), proximity and geographic connection between observations
8 (Hengl et al. 2018).

9 **2.4. Modelling framework**

10 *2.4.1. Classification and Regression models*

11 Random Forest (RF) (Breiman 2001) was used to obtain the probability of the presence
12 of *P. nobilis* and to determine the potential presence area. This model was selected out of
13 four classification methods that were previously tested to identify the most accurate
14 (Gomariz-Castillo, Gim3nez-Casalduero & Alonso-Sarri3a unpub. data): Generalized Lineal
15 Models (GLM), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest (RF) and Regression-
16 Kriging (RK). These methods for variable selection are implemented in the R package *caret*
17 (Kuhn 2015) and are fully described in Hastie et al. (2009) and James et al. (2013). As
18 proposed by Lauria et al. (2017), the abundance (density of individuals) was predicted only
19 in the areas of high probability of presence that were previously estimated using the same
20 methods.

21 RF is a non-parametric algorithm that builds an ensemble of decision trees. Each tree is
22 calibrated using a subsample of cases obtained by bootstrapping. In addition, the features to
23 perform each split are selected from a random subsample of the whole feature set. When all
24 trees have been trained, but not pruned, each new case is analysed by all the trees and the
25 final prediction is obtained as the most frequent result (classification) or by averaging the
26 results (regression). RF uses two parameters: number of trees (n_{tree}), we used the default
27 value (500) since the algorithm is not very sensitive to this parameter (Liaw & Wiener
28 2002), and the number of features randomly sampled in each split (m_{try}). This last
29 parameter was calibrated to maximise the area under the receiver operating characteristic
30 curve (AUC ROC) in the classification and to minimise the root-mean-square error

1 (RMSE) in the regression. It also provides a measure of the importance of the variables
2 reflecting the increase in accuracy that they produce in the model.

3 For the 2013-14 data-set, we used Random Forest Regression-Kriging (RFRK) that
4 includes both a global and a local component. Regression-Kriging (RK) (Hengl et al. 2004)
5 is a spatial prediction technique that combines a regression of the dependent variable on
6 auxiliary variables (global component) with interpolation (OK interpolation) of the
7 regression residuals (local component).

8 Models were calibrated using a K-Block Cross-Validation (K-Block-CV) strategy. This
9 approach attempts to prevent accuracy overestimation due to spatial dependence between
10 training and validation data. Blocks and folds in k-fold-CV are similar; the fundamental
11 difference is that the latter are randomly sampled and the former correspond to spatial
12 subsets. The size of such blocks is defined after an autocorrelation analysis of the study
13 data. This methodology was proposed by Valavi et al. (2019), and is implemented in the R
14 *blockCV* package. The study of the semivariograms revealed that the distance above which
15 it can be considered that there is no spatial autocorrelation is 6,000 m, for this reason, K=6
16 blocks, distributed in nine spatial cells, were generated.

17 To validate the presence/absence models, the area under the ROC function (AUC)
18 (Fielding & Bell 1997), overall accuracy (Acc) and kappa (Cohen 1960) were used. The
19 threshold probability value to decide whether the species was or was not present was
20 calculated using the Youden (1950) method that tries to maximise both specificity and
21 sensitivity. RMSE was used to validate the abundance models. AUC and RMSE were
22 estimated using confidence intervals and the results were used to compare and select the
23 significantly best model.

24 2.4.2. Variable selection

25 Although RF is robust in the face of non-informative or redundant predictors, such
26 features can increase uncertainty, reduce the overall effectiveness of the model (Kuhn &
27 Johnson 2013), increase the difficulty of interpretation and negatively impact parameter
28 estimation. There are two basic approaches to feature selection: filtering and wrapping.

29 Filtering is an approach prior to modelling, in which an importance measure is
30 calculated and the features that do not reach an appropriate value are removed. In this case

1 we used filtering to avoid multicollinearity. In this study, multicollinearity was analysed by
2 estimating a global correlation index obtained by averaging the absolute values of the
3 columns in the correlation matrix (Kuhn & Johnson 2013).

4 Wrapping methods remove features while calibrating the model in order to select the
5 feature set that maximizes model accuracy. Most wrapping methods add or remove features
6 one by one. In Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) (Guyon et al. 2002) features are
7 removed in subsets for efficiency reasons. A model is calibrated and the importance of the
8 features used for its calibration is estimated using RF. All features whose importance is
9 below a given threshold are then removed and the process begins once again until all
10 features in the model are considered important enough. RFE was applied using the
11 previously described cross validation scheme. In RFE, the model is calibrated using all
12 features, then the model goodness of fit (using AUC for classification and RMSE for
13 regression) and feature importance were calculated; the model is then recalculated with just
14 the most important features; these process is repeated recursively until the minimum
15 number of variables that maximize the goodness of fit is obtained.

16 The methodology described was implemented with R software (R Core Team 2018), an
17 Open Source data analysis program, which allows reproducibility to other study areas and
18 data-sets.

19 Using a filtering approach to eliminate multicollinearity, nine out of the 13 initial
20 covariates were selected (Fig. 3). DMAR, SAND, XCOOR and YCOOR) with VIF values
21 higher than 0.9 were removed from the model. Of note is the strong negative correlation
22 between DMAR and SAL (Fig. 3B) ($p < 0.05$, $r = -0.8$) and positive correlation between
23 DMAR and MO (Fig. 3G) ($p < 0.05$, $r = 0.92$), and between DMAR and YCOOR ($p < 0.05$,
24 $r = 0.93$); SAND is highly correlated with SILT (Fig. 3H) ($p < 0.05$, $r = -0.98$) and DALB
25 ($p < 0.05$, $r = -0.84$). Fig. 3 shows the interpolated surface of the 8 included covariates.

26 **3. RESULTS**

27 **3.1. Global evaluation of the models**

28 The model selected to generate the estimated distribution surfaces was RF, with the
29 reduced variable set (after VIF and RFE), for presence/absence data-sets and RFRK for
30 2013-14 density data-set. In the presence-absence models, very high accuracy was reached

1 for the calibration (accuracy = 100% and AUC=0.99); the values of K-fold-CV were high,
2 with AUC = 0.845 ± 0.033 in the 2003-04 data-set and AUC = 0.85 ± 0.025 in the 2013-14
3 data-set. In the case of the density model, values of RMSE = 1.755 and $r^2 = 0.798$ were
4 obtained in calibration; however, the accuracy in K-fold-CV was reduced to $r^2 = 0.162 \pm$
5 0.015 and RMSE = 2.574. In any case, this RMSE value is still relatively low.

6 **3.2. Variable selection and effects of predictors in selected models**

7 In all three cases, six independent variables were selected to explain the spatial
8 distribution of *Pinna nobilis*. The most important variables (most relevant factors) to
9 explain the pattern of distribution were in general the distances to the connections with the
10 Mediterranean (specially DENC and to a lesser extent DEST) and depth (DEPTH).; in the
11 2013-14 data-set, gravel percentage (GRAV) was the most important variable in the
12 distribution of *P. nobilis*.

13 Fig. 4 shows the effects of the predictors on the presence probability of *P. nobilis* for the
14 2003-04 data-set, from the most to the least important predictor. The four most relevant are
15 DENC (Fig. 4A), DEPTH (Fig. 4B) MO (Fig. 4C) and DEST (Fig. 4D), that is, the distance
16 to the entry points of colonisation, depth and organic matter. For the distances to points
17 connecting the Mar Menor and the Mediterranean (DENC, Fig. 4A, and DEST, Fig. 4D), a
18 somewhat stable value is observed with occurrence probabilities of around 0.5 up to a
19 distance of 10,000 m for DENC and 6,000 m for DEST; for larger distances the probability
20 falls off. In the case of depth, a more or less linear increase in the probability of occurrence
21 is observed from the deepest points until a depth of 3.75 m, where maximum probability is
22 reached, after which an inflection point is observed. This curve behaviour seems to be
23 related to a preference for shallow areas masked by anthropic coastal pressure. In the case
24 of organic matter concentration in the sediment (MO, Fig. 4C), there is an increase in the
25 probability of encountering the bivalve when the concentration of MO reaches values
26 higher than 5%. As far as the distance to the coast (DSH, Fig. 4E) is concerned, a
27 maximum preference is observed at a distance of approximately 500 m, a result consistent
28 with that found for the optimum depth. Regarding salinity (SAL, Fig. 4F), the range of
29 salinity in the period 2003-2004 was between 44 - 45 psu and probability of presence of fan
30 mussels decreased with increasing salinity (González-Wangüemert et al. 2009).

1 In the period 2013-2014 (Fig. 5) gravel percentage (GRAV, Fig. 5A) was the most
2 important variable in the distribution of *P. nobilis*. The variables that best explain the
3 distribution of the species in the lagoon based on its presence are: i) the percentage of
4 gravel in the sediment (GRAV, Fig. 5A) with a high probability of occurrence beginning
5 above 10%, ii) the distance to the coast (DSH, Fig. 5B), whose optimum seems to have
6 moved away in relation to the data of the previous period, with the highest probability
7 starting at 1,000 m to the coastline, and the foreseeable influence of the distance from the
8 Encañizadas (DENC, Fig. 5C), while there is a decrease in probability as we move away
9 from this point of connection with the Mediterranean. The same result is observed in
10 relation to the distance to the Estacio channel (DEST, Fig. 5E), which creates a buffer of
11 high probability of encounter in the first 5,000 m from the point of connection. In relation
12 with depth (DEPTH, Fig. 5F), probability was higher from 3 m depth. The pattern in
13 relation to salinity (SAL, Fig. 5D) shows a higher probability of occurrence in areas of
14 higher salinity, within the range that characterizes the lagoon although the differences are
15 subtle.

16 The specimen density results (Fig. 6) show similar patterns to those found with the
17 presence-absence model in terms of distance to the channels (DENC, Fig. 6A) and to
18 Estacio (DEST, Fig. 6F) or distance to the coastline (DSH, Fig. 6E), parameters such as
19 salinity (SAL, Fig. 6B) have an opposite behaviour, there is a *P. nobilis* high density with
20 minimum salinity values within the range described in the lagoon, and there is a peak of
21 bivalve density associated with silt percentage around 40% and organic matter (MO, Fig.
22 6D) of 4% in sediment.

23 **3.3. Spatial prediction**

24 Figs. 7A and 7B represent the potential distribution of *P. nobilis* according to the
25 predicted probability of occurrence and the potential zone, obtained from the
26 reclassification of the probability using Youden (1950) method as cut-off (0.501 in 2003-04
27 and 0.503 in 2013-14). It should be noted that, although one of the advantages of RF is that
28 it predicts the presence or absence of the species at all the observed points, the reliability of
29 the resulting surface will depend on the quality of the sampled data; therefore, the
30 distribution in 2003-04 (Fig. 7A), which was obtained in a sampling carried out with an aim

1 other than the observation of *P. nobilis*, may be less reliable. However, the results obtained
2 in 2003-04 after the resampling process and its modelling allow a better understanding of
3 the potential distribution of *P. nobilis* with respect to the partial studies existing in this
4 period.

5 Comparing the potential area in 2003-04 (Fig. 7A, 2,985 ha, 22% of the Mar Menor
6 coastal lagoon) with that for 2013-14 (Fig. 7B, 7,385 ha, 54.7% of the Mar Menor coastal
7 lagoon), a concentration in the northern part of the lagoon, limited by the central islands,
8 appears in the first sampling, the only exception being a point where the presence of the
9 bivalve is evident next to the entrance of La Gola channel connection.

10 This spatial pattern could be explained by the high probability of the bivalve being
11 present at the entrances to the lagoon (main routes of entry) and their gradual expansion
12 towards the other areas. In 2013-14 (Fig. 8), although the southward expansion is evident,
13 the highest probability is still observed in the areas closest to the entrances (main routes of
14 entry), which is consistent with the effects shown in Fig 6. A secondary maximum appears
15 to the north of the islands. There is also a southward tendency to spread from the entrances
16 to the islands, and a gradual expansion from there, again towards the south, which may be
17 related to the colonization pattern. The density model estimates values that vary between
18 0.01-21.6 ind/100m², and an average density of 2.181±0.004 ind/100m² (excluding density
19 values outside the potential distribution area in 2013-14), so the total estimated number in
20 the lagoon for 2013-14 is 1,609,943±3,309 individuals.

21
22 To complete this study, a preliminary sampling was carried out after the eutrophic
23 collapse of 2016 (Fig. 9). Thirteen of the samples correspond to stations with presence of *P.*
24 *nobilis* (squares in Fig. 9) and four stations with absence (triangles in Fig. 9). A 100%
25 mortality was observed in the 17, 35% stations deeper than 3 m, that is the threshold of the
26 "severe eutrophication" area (Fig. 9). In shallow sampling stations, 60 *P. nobilis* individuals
27 were counted; only 5 (8.79%) of the found specimens were alive.

28 **4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS**

29 The population of *Pinna nobilis* has been greatly reduced in most Mediterranean areas in
30 the past few decades due to the human pressure (García-March et al. 2007, Katsanevakis

1 2007, Katsanevakis & Thessalou-Legaki 2009, Rabaoui et al. 2011). However, from 1983,
2 first observation in the lagoon (Rodríguez Babio & Navarro Tárrega 1983), to 2014, the
3 Mar Menor has witnessed colonization and stabilization of the "fan mussel", with a total of
4 7,385 ha of potential habitat. In order to understand this process of *P. nobilis* colonization
5 in the Mar Menor, it is necessary to interpret the dispersion model and the influence of the
6 main factors that determine the colonization process.

7 Some of the most common mechanisms for species transfer in near shore water include
8 the movement of alien communities on ship bottoms or the connection of waterways
9 through artificial channels (Ruiz et al. 1997). The establishment of foreign species lead the
10 major changes in the composition of the fauna of many closed and semi closed areas such
11 as the estuaries, harbours and coastal lagoons of the western Mediterranean (Cognetti &
12 Maltagliati 2000). This invasion could occur after years to decades of dispersal
13 opportunities from source to recipient region. The successful establishment of alien species
14 often requires many inoculations, and success will depend partly upon inoculant size, the
15 physiological condition of individuals, and local conditions at the time of arrival
16 (Roughgarden 1986). Clearly, the artificial expansion of the Estacio channel has caused the
17 entrance of numerous species into the lagoon. The drop in salinity due to the greater
18 exchange of water with the Mediterranean has generated more favourable conditions for the
19 survival of these species (Gimenez-Casalduero et al. 2016). In the case of *P. nobilis*, the
20 channels seem to have played an important role in the entry of larvae from the nearby
21 Mediterranean populations. The results of this study show that not only the artificial
22 channel of El Estacio, but the natural channel "Encañizadas" has also been an important
23 gateway to the lagoon.

24 The salinity tolerance range for *P. nobilis* has been described as between 35 and 42 psu
25 (Schlieper et al. 1960, Butler et al. 1993). It is reasonable to think that this species could not
26 support the high salinity levels (average values of 52 psu) in the lagoon before opening the
27 Estacio channel (Aravio-Torre & Arévalo 1971). But the presence of the "fan mussel" since
28 the early 1980s, few years after opening the communication channel between the two water
29 bodies and just as the salinity in the lagoon began to fall to reach an average value of 44.5
30 psu (Azzati et al. 1987), demonstrates that the upper limit of tolerance of this bivalve is
31 well above the previously described values (Schlieper et al. 1960, Butler et al. 1993). In the

1 present work we verify that *P. nobilis* colonized the lagoon widely, withstanding a salinity
2 range between 44 and 45 psu for several decades (1983-2014) before the eutrophication
3 crisis occurred. Their preference for less saline areas within this range is likely to be due to
4 the distance from colonization points rather than salinity in itself. The individuals in the
5 Mar Menor population may grow to larger sizes than other populations because they are
6 typically sheltered from detrimental hydrodynamics (García-March et al. 2020).

7 From the first moment of colonization until the beginning of the 2000s, the distribution
8 of the individuals was marked by the distance to the entry points “Encañizadas” and Estacio
9 channels (DENC and DEST), probably because larvae enter through these points from the
10 population located in the Mediterranean side and whose largest population was along a
11 coastal strip of approximately 500 m from the coast (DSH) and at 4 m depth (DEPTH).

12 The distribution of *P. nobilis* is usually patchy (de Gaulejac & Vicente 1990, Butler et
13 al. 1993) and it is known that recruitment is influenced by environmental factors that
14 synchronize spawning (Philippart et al. 2003; Cabanellas-Reboredo et al. 2009). Premise
15 that is currently being analysed in the Mar Menor by these researchers. In the lagoon the
16 specimen’s size inside a group seemed fairly homogeneous, which suggests that
17 recruitment occurred in pulses, probably associated to key events of favourable
18 environmental conditions in the lagoon. Rising seawater temperatures could affect
19 recruitment (Philippart et al. 2003). Fluctuating temperatures, which are common in the
20 lagoon, can be determinant in the reproductive processes of *P. nobilis*, and it is important to
21 observe the relationship between environmental factors such as temperature and fan mussel
22 spawning and recruitment periods (de Gaulejac 1993, Richardson et al. 1999).

23 During the first decades, after the entry of the first specimens into the lagoon, the
24 connection channels with the Mediterranean (Estacio and Encañizadas) appeared to be an
25 important entry pathway for larvae coming from the large population of fan mussel existing
26 at that time in the Mediterranean *Posidonia oceanica* meadow in front of the lagoon. After
27 the colonization resulting from larvae coming from the Mediterranean, during 2013-2014
28 the specimens reached reproductive maturity and began to colonize areas farther from the
29 points of entry and the coastline (DSH) and the optimal depth of population distribution
30 increased because they colonized deeper areas (DEPTH). Of interest is the fact that one of
31 the main factors that explains the population in 2013-2014 is the presence of gravel. The

1 high correlation between the distribution of fan mussel and the presence of high levels of
2 gravel (GRAV) in the sediment can be explained by the fact that although it is common in
3 sandy areas (Katsanevakis 2004), it needs to be attached by its numerous byssus filaments
4 to large particles, seagrass rhizomes or solid substratum structures (Katsanevakis &
5 Thessalou-Legaki 2009; Basso et al. 2015b). The Mar Menor is characterized by the
6 presence in many areas of a high concentration of particles such as gravel of conchiferous
7 origin and many of the specimens in the lagoon are attached to *Cymodocea nodosa*
8 rhizomes but also *Bittium reticulatum* or others fragments of shells (García-March, 2003).

9 In the present work, a highly significant inverse relationship has been described between
10 the potential distribution of the bivalve until 2016 and the distance to the higher eutrophic
11 and hypoxic point in the lagoon (ALB: the mouth of the Rambla del Albuji3n). Although
12 this variable has been removed from the models after detecting a high collinearity in the
13 VIF analysis with the XCOOR variable and the texture variables (SAND; SILT). The
14 mouth of the Rambla del Albuji3n (ALB) is a point where the oxygen reached an average
15 value of 5 mg O₂L⁻¹, and minimum values of 0.47 mg O₂L⁻¹ (Velasco et al. 2006). Even
16 some studies have demonstrated that juveniles of *P. nobilis* are relatively resistant to
17 moderate exposure to hypoxia (3.07 mg O₂L⁻¹) (Basso et al. 2015a).

18 However, all the processes of colonization and establishment of *P. nobilis* in the lagoon
19 were interrupted by two simultaneous events in the Mar Menor area and the Mediterranean
20 during 2016: i) the dramatic episode of eutrophication that caused a high mortality of
21 specimens and; ii) the mass mortality event of *P. nobilis* in the south western
22 Mediterranean Sea that caused the disappearance of the important population that for years
23 had been an important source of larvae towards the lagoon.

24 A survey conducted between April and June 2017 confirmed a mortality of more than
25 90% of adult individuals in the lagoon. Two different situations can be observed. First, no
26 living individuals were found below 2.5 m. in depth, even in areas where, until 2014, there
27 had been a strong likelihood of individuals appearing (Fig. 9). This depth coincides with
28 that described by Belando et al. (2017), which confirmed the total disappearance of benthic
29 macrophytes below an average of 2.5 m depth in the whole lagoon, after the eutrophication
30 episode of 2016 and its replacement by extremely slimy and anoxic sediment. It is highly
31 probable that in these areas, the loss of light produced by the high concentration of

1 phytoplankton in the water column was responsible for the death of the macrophytes, while
2 the decomposition of the organic matter led to intense anoxia processes that caused the
3 death of the macrofauna, including *P. nobilis*.

4 However, in the population located above 3 m depth, a survival rate of 10% was
5 estimated (Fig. 9), which is higher than that described for populations affected by
6 *Haplosporidium* in the Mediterranean (Vázquez-Luis et al. 2017). Although it is necessary
7 to carry out many more tests on the survivors, during 2017 only one analysis of PCR was
8 performed to a lagoon individual to and it was negative to the presence of *Haplosporidium*
9 *pinnae* (Catanese et al. 2018). But no analysis of mycobacterium has been carried out in
10 that period. No infective cells were detected in the digestive gland or hemocytosis that
11 might suggest the existence of infection. However, an infection of the gills by ciliated
12 protozoa (saprophytic opportunistic parasites) was observed, possibly as a consequence of
13 the existing high organic load. To carry out tests to detect mycobacterium could help to
14 resolve many doubts about mortality in the lagoon. Despite the significant decline in
15 population due to the lagoon's environmental collapse in 2016, the stock of survivors is
16 sufficient to begin a captive breeding program. The problem is that four years after the
17 eutrophication crisis, the situation has not improved. Assuming that the environmental
18 conditions of the lagoon will be restored, the preliminary data of this research could help
19 make the Mar Menor an important reservoir of *P. nobilis* in the western Mediterranean.
20 The lagoon is one of the few remaining sites where fan mussels still survive the disease, so
21 maintaining good environmental conditions and healthy fan mussel populations should be a
22 priority. The initiatives currently promoted by the responsible administrations, aimed at
23 decreasing the levels of nutrients in the lagoon and consequently seeking an environmental
24 recovery, have not currently been implemented. The survival of the species in the lagoon
25 depends on its good environmental condition. Therefore, the application of the necessary
26 measures for the recovery of the lagoon and the restoration of the fan mussel population is a
27 priority and urgent. At the same time, it is important to continue with ex situ conservation
28 actions and projects to achieve breeding in captivity.

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1 **7. TABLES**

2 Table 1. Main characteristics of the information sources used

Data-set	Campaign (year)	Method	Source	Number of presence points	Number of absence points	Total number of points
Historical	1983	Visual	Rodríguez Babio & Navarro Tarrega (1983)	1	0	1
	2003-2004	SCUBA diving; Snorkel transects; bathyscaphe	CARM (2003)	34	49	83
Integrated 2013-14	2013	SCUBA diving; Aquaplane; Bathyscaphe	Specific survey	31	29	60
	2014	SCUBA diving	Belando et al. (2014)	21	36	57
2016	2016	SCUBA diving	Specific survey	11	6	17

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1 **8. FIGURES**
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Fig. 1. Location of Mar Menor coastal lagoon.

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Fig. 2. Sampling survey. (A) 2003 data (Rodríguez Babio & Navarro Tarrega 1983, CARM 2003), including all points, the points obtained by resampling and the 5 cluster areas used to resample, obtained using the hierarchical cluster-based method; (B) 2013 data (specific campaign conducted in this research); (C) 2014 data (Belando et al. 2014); (D) Integrated 2013-14 data-set.

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Fig. 3. Environmental variables used as predictors in the models. The nine variables selected after multicollinearity filtering are included. Acronyms in section 2.3 (Environmental data).

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 2 Fig. 4. Effects of predictors in the Random Forest presence-absence model with the
 3 variables selected by RFE. 2003-04. The variables are ordered from highest to lowest
 4 importance in the model. The rest of the variables are not considered relevant. Acronyms in
 5 section 2.3 (Environmental data).
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 2 **Fig. 5.** Effects of predictors in the Random Forest presence-absence model with the
 3 variables selected by RFE. 2013-14. The variables are ordered from highest to lowest
 4 importance in the model. The rest of the variables are not considered relevant. Acronyms in
 5 section 2.3 (Environmental data).
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Fig. 6. Effects of predictors in the Random Forest population density model with the
variables selected by RFE. 2014. The variables are ordered from highest to lowest
importance in the model. The rest of the variables are not considered relevant. Acronyms in
section 2.3 (Environmental data).

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Fig. 7. Spatial prediction for *P. nobilis*. (A, B) potential distribution for *P. nobilis* in 2003-04 and 2013-14; presence-absence RF models with variable selection; line-shaded areas refer to potential areas (probability of occurrence above the cutoff point). (c) Spatial prediction of density for *P. nobilis*, 2013-14 data-set; RFRK model with variable selection using potential areas in 2013-14 as mask.

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Fig. 8. Spatial prediction of density for *P. nobilis*, 2013-14 data-set; RFRK model with variable selection using potential areas in 2013-14 as mask.

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Fig. 9. Potential distribution in 2013-14 (presence-absence RF model and potential areas -probability of occurrence above the cutoff point-) versus 2017 data. Data sampled in 2017 (red and yellow squares, pink triangles) and data sampled in 2013-2014 (black dots and triangles) are included. The "severe eutrophication" area (line-shaded areas) refers to areas below -3 m in depth.